

MAKING FINANCE INVISIBLE: EMBEDDED FINANCE ADOPTION AND USER EXPERIENCE

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

If you have ever made a payment on an e-commerce platform or a ride-hailing app without using cash, purchased something using a Buy-Now-Pay-Later offering or used a price-freeze option on an online travel or airline platform, you have used Embedded Finance (EF). It is a growing phenomenon, with annual revenue of \$22 billion expected to grow to \$51 billion by 2026 (Harris et al., 2022) and with surging online-search interest (Ozili, 2022).

Improved User Experience (UX) is seen as one of the key reasons for its adoption and proliferation, creating opportunities for financial institutions, fintech companies and digital platforms ecosystems. Despite its importance, EF does not have a consistent definition, research is sparse with only 4 published academic articles mentioning EF while a plethora of practitioner and industry research and grey literature fills the void.

Research Gap:

- Lack of a consistent EF definition in academic literature & very little academic research
- Empirical testing needed on whether technical aspect of EF matches user perception of EF
- Empirical testing needed on User Experience element of EF adoption seen as key driver
- Drivers of adoption of technology and fintech have been studied using theoretical frameworks like Technology Acceptance Model and the Unified Theory of Acceptance & Use of Technology but lack of research combining this with actual usability metrics into the model

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

Figure 1. Technical and Perceived Embedded Finance

Constructs Used

Clicks:

- **Definition:** Effort taken by the end user when clicking or tapping their input device, as a mouse or touching pad (Harrati et al., 2016)
- **Measurement:** A single type of click is considered, referring to both right or left while a double click is counted as two consecutive clicks.
- **Hypothesis Development:** Taking from HCI, per de Santana & Baranauskas (2015), usage data determined from client side user logs for usability evaluation are reliable and efficient metrics for usability insights.

Task Duration:

- **Definition:** Total time taken to achieve a particular task by a user or usability expert, usually used to measure efficiency rate (Harrati et al., 2016)
- **Measurement:** Approximated in seconds as difference between time stamps for the start and last data logs for a task.

- **Hypothesis Development:** Same as Clicks

Completion Rate:

- **Definition:** Success rate of completion of tasks, one of the fundamental usability metrics for user to successfully achieve a goal.
- **Measurement:** Percentage of success measured as:
- **Hypothesis Development:** Same as Clicks

Usability:

- **Definition:** Usability of a software product is the extent to which the product is convenient and practical to use (Boehm et al., 1978).
- **Measurement:** Equal weightage applied to Completion Rate, Clicks and Task Duration
- **Hypothesis Development:** Same as Clicks.

Performance Expectancy:

- **Definition:** Degree to which using an Embedded Finance will provide benefit to consumer in online retailer transactions (modified from - Venkatesh et al., (2014))
- **Measurement:** Likert scale with a range of 1 to 7; 1 as strongly disagree and 7 as strongly agree
 - o Using this product would be useful
 - o Using this product would increase my effectiveness
 - o Using this product would help me pay more quickly
- **Hypothesis Development:** According to UTAUT2, performance expectancy can influence consumer adoption of technology products as consumers evaluate technology mediated task performance based on its advantages like efficiency, effectiveness and productivity, and cost, including in behavioral investment.

Effort Expectancy:

- **Definition:** Degree of ease associated with consumers' use of technology (Venkatesh et al., 2014)
- **Measurement:** Likert scale with a range of 1 to 7; 1 as strongly disagree and 7 as strongly agree
 - o Learning to use this product is easy for me
 - o It would be easy for me to become skillful at using this product
 - o I would find this product easy to use
- **Hypothesis Development:** Per UTAUT2, EE can influence consumer adoption of technology products as consumers evaluate technology based on its perceived ease of use as it is assumed to make lives better.

Facilitating Conditions:

- **Definition:** Consumers Perceptions of the resources and support available to perform a behavior (Venkatesh et al., 2014)
- **Measurement:** Likert scale with a range of 1 to 7; 1 as strongly disagree and 7 as strongly agree
 - o I have the resources necessary to use this product
 - o I have the knowledge necessary to use this product
 - o This product is compatible with the device I use
- **Hypothesis Development:** Per UTAUT2, FC can influence consumer adoption of technology products as FC enhance perception that technology products are effortless and easy to operate.

Innovativeness:

- **Definition:** Propensity to try new products (Manning, Bearden & Madden, 1995).
- **Measurement:** Likert scale with a range of 1 to 7; 1 as strongly disagree and 7 as strongly agree
- Among my peers, I am usually the first to try out new products
- In general, I am hesitant to change my established routines
- New products are making our lives more exciting
- **Hypothesis Development:** Behavioral science suggests personality traits like personal innovativeness may be significant determinants of adoption (Kovarikova, Grosova, & Bara, 2017).

Perceived Security:

- **Definition:** Customer perception of the process of system and product design to securely protect consumer information (Mohamad et al., 2018).
- **Measurement:** Likert scale with a range of 1 to 7; 1 as strongly disagree and 7 as strongly agree
 - o I feel completely secure operating with this product
 - o This product is a secure means for sharing sensitive information
 - o My safety concerns are only with this product
- **Hypothesis Development:** In extensions to UTAUT2, perceptions about the technology security system are seen as important to gain consumer trust against unauthorized access and to minimize risk (Lee et al., 2011)

Behavioral Intention to Use:

- **Definition:** Consumer intention to adopt new technology (Venkatesh et al., 2014)
- **Measurement:** Likert scale with a range of 1 to 7; 1 as strongly disagree and 7 as strongly agree
 - o I will use / continue using this product in the future

- During the next six (6) months, I intend to use this product
 - Five (5) years from now, I intend to be using this product
 - I encourage others to use this product
- **Hypothesis Development:** Taken from UTAUT2

METHODOLOGY

The study will consider existing literature and propose a new definition for EF (findings covered in detail in the following section). The study then plans to collect data using a controlled experiment and questionnaire survey (to be pursued after ATC).

Invite respondents (n=200) to:

- Test 3 EF products on an online platform
- Consent to client-side logging of usability data (using addition of short JavaScript code or to their browser or browser add-on by clicking after consenting) while they test the products
- Fill out questionnaire survey after each product test

The study intends to use online usability platform to conduct the above study, including a cash incentive for participants which can be collected through the online platform targeting required parameters (e.g demographics).

The study will then use Structured Equation Modeling using SPSS to analyze the technical EF data (using Usability metrics) and perceived EF data (using questionnaire survey) and test hypotheses.

FINDINGS

Scholarly research and a host of practitioner, industry sources and grey literature defines Embedded Finance in various, sometimes conflicting ways. We divide these into four schools of thought.

Figure 2. Schools of Thought on Embedded Finance (own illustration)

#	SOURCE	TYPE	DEFINITION	SCHOOL
1	Sam et al., (2020) in Journal of Information Technology Management	Academic Journal	"Mobile finance functions offered by non-bank third-party financial service providers"...which "are organizations that have no direct relationship with government and banks."	1
2	Sullivan (2022) in Plaid	Grey Literature	"Embedded finance is non-financial companies offering financial products and services. It could be an e-commerce merchant providing insurance, a coffee shop app that offers 1-click payments, or a department store's branded credit card."	1
3	Wullweber (2020) in Cultural Economy	Academic Journal	"The Shadow Banking system"	1
4	Dolgorukov (2021) in Forbes	Grey Literature	"Embedded finance is the use of financial tools or services — such as lending or payment processing — by a non-financial provider"	1
5	Dresner et al., (2022) in McKinsey Insights	Grey Literature	"Embedded finance is the placing of a financial product in a nonfinancial customer experience, journey, or platform."	2
6	Lee (2022) in Euromoney	Grey Literature	Bank and non-bank lenders offering Loans to customers buying both online and at physical points of sale"...including "business loans and working capital lines".	2

7	Honig (2021) in Best's Review	Grey Literature	"Distribution of financial service product through someone else's customer experience"	2
8	Stripe (2023) in Stripe	Grey Literature	"When a software platform uses a BaaS provider, this is typically called "embedded finance" because the platform adds the financial services as part of its core software."	2
9	Open Payd (2023) in Open Payd Blog	Grey Literature	"Embedded finance is the integration of financial services directly into a business's products and services, via API. This enables both financial and non-financial businesses to offer services like payments, banking, lending and insurance without becoming regulated as financial entities or building any financial infrastructure themselves"	2
10	Mambu (2023) in Mambu AWS	Grey Literature	"Embedded Finance enables any brand, business, or merchant to rapidly, and at low cost, integrate innovative financial services into new propositions and customer experiences."	2
11	Fava (2023) in Journal of Financial Planning	Professional Journal	"Embedded finance takes traditional financial services capabilities and places them inside consumer apps, making it quick and easy for everyday consumers to access them."	3
12	Meng et al., (2021) in Microprocessors and Microsystems	Academic Journal	"Financial service on the terms of the customer, from anywhere, anytime. There is no longer a need to visit banks that have access to their money. In some cases embedded finance eliminates traditional banks".	3
13	Jacobson (2022) in builtin	Grey Literature	"Embedded finance is the integration of financial services like lending, payment processing or insurance into nonfinancial businesses' infrastructures without the need to redirect to traditional financial institutions"	3

14	Hensen & Kotting (2022) in Journal of Digital Banking	Professional Journal	Banks addressing "consumers right at their 'point of need' - on e-commerce platforms, in apps from mobility service providers or on comparison portals"... "by embedding financial services into the products of non-bank companies, thus offering seamless processes and an increased level of convenience to their clients. Open Banking is what provides the foundation for this concept of 'embedded finance'".	4
15	Crosman (2021) in American Banker	Grey Literature	Products "embedded in other things and places they go, with banks unseen in the background"	4
16	Haselwood (2022) in The Global Treasurer	Grey Literature	"Embedded finance refers to the shift from time-consuming bank transfers to the use of financial services or tools by a non-financial provider"... and "should create more simplicity and convenience by embedding the financial journey into a customer's normal non-financial journey".	4
17	Carbonnier (2022) in Fintech Futures	Grey Literature	"Embedded finance is the integration of financial services or tools – traditionally obtained via a bank – within the products or services of a non-financial organisation. Think of an online store offering short-term loans in the form of BNPL, or the digital wallet on your phone enabling instant contactless payments"	4
18	Harris et al., (2022) Bain and Company Insights	Grey Literature	"A nonfinancial software platform providing an adjacent financial service, for which it takes some degree of economic ownership. This allows the platform's customers to take advantage of a value-added offering within the native customer journey."	4

19	Sieber and Guibaud (2022)	Book	"Embedded Finance" is embedded in another context - a checkout line, a mobile app etc. From consumer perspective, it could be summarized as "invisible payments" or "invisible finance" because key message is that the financial transaction becomes naturally integrated into what you are doing to the point it feels invisible."	4
20	Jones (2020) in 11FS	Grey Literature	"Embedded Finance isn't really designed to be finance at all. When you create a user journey that addresses common pain points - whatever that may be - and you happen to incorporate a financial element, that's embedded finance. The end user shouldn't really notice the finance if it's properly embedded; it just becomes part of the product"	4
21	Rise (2021) in Rise Fintech Insights by Barclays	Grey Literature	" Embedded Finance allows companies to create innovative financial offerings that are integrated into the act of purchasing a non-financial product or service."	4

School 1 definition is viewed as too broad. In practice, financial offerings by third parties can be provided outside of mobile technology and can also be provided in partnership with traditional financial institutions and fintech under a Banking as a Service (Baas) infrastructure. It also does not cover the fact that most of these offerings benefit from being offered at the point of context, on third party platforms like e-commerce and consumer applications where users organically congregate.

School 2 does not adequately cover the improvement in user experience angle. In practice, just providing financial services on third party platforms does not illustrate why user adoption is rising so strongly. Traditional financial institutions have been distributing financial services at the point of context in offline world for decades, via for example auto-financing options at car dealerships or educational loans offered in collaboration with universities without the same growth.

School 3 is not viewed as going far enough as technology has the potential to revolutionize the user experience and distribution of financial services, rather than just introducing incremental improvements. As digital applications, Internet of

Things (IoT) get more ubiquitous, user experience should move towards seamless, rather than just better.

School 4 offers the most all-encompassing definition of Embedded Finance but it suffers from pitfalls, as practical evolution to this ideal can be across a spectrum. A non-financial platform may be able to offer one-click checkout, Uber may be able to offer instant payment once the cab door is closed but these are ideals achieved on the second transaction, after a user provides card or bank account credentials manually typed at checkout on the first transactions to be stored on file or tokenized. Therefore, there is a need to keep the definition open and account for the spectrum of Embedded Finance offerings.

A New Definition of Embedded Finance

For the purpose of this study, we will use a new and amended definition of Embedded Finance that combines the appropriate elements of the four schools while accounting for the shortcomings outlined in Section 2.2. Embedded Finance is defined as (a) financial products and services, (b) offered by non-financial companies or in partnership with traditional financial institutions and fintech companies (taken from School 1 and 2, (c) at the point of context on digital platforms and applications where users organically congregate (taken from School 2), (d) with improved user experience at the core of the proposition (taken from School 3), (e) ideally naturally integrated into a non-financial product or service to the point of feeling invisible and seamless (taken from School 4). This new definition means Embedded Finance offerings can be viewed across a spectrum, illustrated as follows:

Figure 3. Traditional and Embedded Finance

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